

An Investigation of the Motivational Dynamics of Preparatory School Students Learning English as a Foreign Language

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<p>ARTICLE HISTORY</p> <p>Received 17 Mar 2026 Accepted 30 Apr 2026</p> <p>KEYWORDS</p> <p>foreign language learning; language learning motivation; EFL learners; English preparation programs; motivation dynamics</p>	<p>ABSTRACT</p> <p>Motivation for foreign language learning is considered one of the most influential factors in students' participation in their learning process and academic success. Motivation plays a critical role, particularly for students enrolled in university preparatory programs, due to the intensive and demanding nature of the educational process. However, the literature reveals only a limited number of studies that comprehensively examine the motivational dynamics of preparatory school students. Therefore, this study aims to examine the motivational dynamics of students who are enrolled in university English preparatory programs and the factors that increase or decrease their motivation. The research was conducted using a mixed-methods design. In the quantitative phase, a Likert-type questionnaire was administered to 219 students, while in the qualitative phase, semi-structured focus group interviews were conducted with 50 students. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were examined using thematic analysis. The findings revealed that the vast majority of students had a strong motivation to learn English and considered it important, particularly in terms of career opportunities, international communication, and personal development. However, intensive course programs, exam pressures, and language learning difficulties were identified as the main factors that negatively affect motivation. The results obtained indicate that creating more interactive and student-centred learning environments in preparatory programs could positively support students' motivation and language learning processes.</p>
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Introduction

Foreign language learning is a complex process that offers significant opportunities in individuals' academic, social and professional lives. Many factors influence learners' success in this process, and motivation is considered among the most decisive ones. Motivation is a fundamental psychological factor that influences individuals' desire to learn a language, the effort they put into the learning process and their determination in the face of difficulties encountered during the learning process. Research shows that highly motivated students participate more actively in the language learning process, use more learning strategies and are more successful in language learning (Dörnyei, 2020; Othman, 2025).

The importance of motivation in foreign language learning becomes even more apparent when it comes to a global communication language, such as English. Today, English plays a significant role in academic studies, international communication and career opportunities. For this reason, many universities offer preparatory programmes to ensure that students acquire the necessary language skills before they begin their academic education. Preparatory schools provide a significant learning environment for students to develop their academic English proficiency. However, the intensive and demanding nature of these programmes can cause changes in students' motivation levels over time. Research shows that many students start learning English with high motivation, but this motivation can decrease for various reasons as the learning process progresses (Dörnyei, 2020; Matsuda & Gobel, 2004). It is

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particularly noted that students in university preparatory programmes can experience a significant loss of motivation, which negatively affects their learning process.

Language learning motivation is influenced by numerous factors, including students' personal goals, perceptions of self-efficacy, teaching methods, classroom environment and teacher-student interaction. Furthermore, students' perceptions of how much they will use English in their academic and professional lives can also shape their motivation. Students' perceptions and experiences of the learning environment can also play an important role in their motivation. Indeed, research shows that the learning environment, teaching strategies and students' attitudes towards language learning directly affect motivation (Kayır et al., 2025).

Recent developments in the field of education, and particularly global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have significantly impacted language learning processes and student motivation. During the pandemic, many educational institutions transitioned to online learning environments, leading to changes in students' learning experiences. Research indicates that online learning environments can have a significant impact on students' motivation and anxiety levels (MacIntyre et al., 2020). This process has highlighted how sensitive language learning motivation is to contextual factors.

Although there are numerous studies on language learning motivation, a significant portion of this research has focused on general English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. Studies examining the motivational dynamics of students attending university preparatory schools are relatively limited. Furthermore, some of the existing studies focus solely on quantitative data and do not sufficiently address qualitative data that would reveal students' motivational experiences in more depth. In this context, examining the motivation of students enrolled in English preparatory programmes at universities is important from both a theoretical and practical perspective. Identifying the factors that influence student motivation can help teachers develop more effective teaching strategies and encourage students to participate more actively in the learning process. Furthermore, such studies can help preparatory programmes to create a more student-centred and motivating learning environment.

In line with this, this study aims to examine the motivational dynamics of university English preparatory school students, identifying the elements that increase and decrease students' motivation in the learning process. Simply, the research seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the motivational dynamics of English preparatory school students towards learning English?
2. What factors increase and decrease the motivation of English preparatory school students to learn English?

Literature Review

Foreign language learning is a multidimensional process in which many cognitive, affective and social factors play a role. Among these factors, motivation is considered one of the most important variables affecting students' participation in the learning process, their learning efforts and their success in language learning. Motivation is a fundamental psychological factor that determines students' desire to learn a language, the time they devote to the learning process and their determination to continue learning despite the difficulties they encounter (Dörnyei, 2020; Gardner, 2010). Research on language learning motivation shows that students with high levels of motivation participate more actively in the learning process, use more learning strategies and are more successful in language learning (Ushioda, 2011; Lamb, 2017).

One of the first comprehensive theoretical frameworks to explain language learning motivation is the socio-educational model developed by R.C. Gardner. According to Gardner, motivation is related to an individual's desire to learn a language, the effort they put into the process, and

their positive attitude towards the learning process (Gardner, 1985). In Gardner's model, motivation is addressed under two basic dimensions: intrinsic motivation and instrumental motivation. Intrinsic motivation is related to the individual's self-desire to connect with the culture where the target language is spoken. Whereas instrumental motivation refers to the individual's desire to learn the language for pragmatic purposes such as academic success and career opportunities (Gardner, 2010). This model has formed the basic theoretical framework for foreign language motivation research for many years.

Research on motivation has been approached through various theoretical frameworks over time. In this context, the Second Language Motivational Self-System developed by Dörnyei has emerged as an important model for explaining language learning motivation (Dörnyei, 2009). This model consists of three main components: the ideal second language (L2) self, the obligatory L2 self and the learning experience. The ideal L2 expresses the individual's dream of becoming a person who can use the language effectively in the future, while the obligatory L2 expresses the individual's responsibility to learn the language due to their social environment or academic requirements. The learning experience encompasses factors such as the classroom environment, teaching methods and teacher-student interaction (Dörnyei, 2020). This model emphasises that motivation is not a static trait, but a dynamic process that can change over time.

A significant portion of studies on language learning motivation are also addressed within the framework of Self-Determination Theory. According to this theory, developed by Ryan and Deci, individuals' motivations are divided into two basic categories: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2017). Intrinsic motivation is related to an individual performing an activity solely because they are interested in it and enjoy it. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is explained as an individual performing an activity due to external factors such as rewards, success, or social expectations. Research conducted in the context of language learning shows that intrinsic motivation contributes to students' more active participation in the learning process and to their achieving more lasting success in learning (Ryan and Deci, 2017; Noels, 2013).

Numerous studies examining the role of motivation in the language learning process have revealed a strong relationship between motivation and academic achievement. Students with high levels of motivation participate more actively in the learning process and are more resilient in the face of challenges encountered during learning (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011). Furthermore, students' perceptions of self-efficacy, attitudes towards learning and future goals also have a significant impact on motivation (Bandura, 1997; Ushioda, 2011). Therefore, motivation is considered as one of the key factors determining success in foreign language learning.

Certain studies have shown that motivation is not merely an individual trait, but rather a dynamic process influenced by social and contextual factors (Dörnyei and Ryan, 2015). Students' motivation can change over time, and this change can be influenced by various factors such as learning experiences, success or failure. In particular, the classroom environment, teaching methods and teacher-student interaction are among the factors that directly affect students' motivation. Student-centred teaching approaches and interaction-based learning activities increase student motivation, while monotonous teaching methods and exam-focused education can negatively affect motivation (Lamb, 2017; Dörnyei and Ryan, 2015).

Studies conducted in the context of EFL indicate that students' motivation to learn English is influenced by various individual and environmental factors. Students' perception of English as an international language of communication and their need for English in line with their academic and professional goals are among the important factors that increase motivation

(Kormos and Csizér, 2008). However, exam anxiety, low self-efficacy perceptions and limited opportunities for students to use the language in their daily lives can negatively affect motivation (MacIntyre, 2002; Öztürk & Gürbüz, 2013).

Research conducted in the Turkish context also indicates that the motivation levels of university preparatory school students are closely related to their language learning success. Studies conducted on university students' perceptions about motivational strategies could be different according to various factors (Erdil-Moody & Thompson, 2020). In particular, students' perception of English as an important tool for international communication and academic success is among the factors that increase motivation. However, an intensive course programme, exam pressure and limited opportunities for students to use the language in their daily lives can have negative effects on motivation (Öztürk & Gürbüz, 2013).

In conclusion, studies in the field reveal that motivation plays a central role in foreign language learning and directly influences the learning process. However, there is still a need for research into how motivation is shaped in different learning contexts and among different groups of students. Studies examining the motivational dynamics of students attending university preparatory schools are particularly limited. Therefore, research examining the motivation of preparatory school students towards learning English and the factors influencing this motivation is expected to make significant contributions to the field.

Methodology

This research adopted a mixed-methods design, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection approaches to investigate motivational dynamics in the EFL learning context. This design was adopted to maintain a holistic and comprehensive understanding of the motivational orientations of learners, integrating statistical data with rich contextual narratives. This approach aligns with the growing use in educational research to justify knowledge assertions and enhance the credibility and richness of findings (Subedi, 2016). Similarly, in line with Creswell (2012), this study strengthens its credibility through explicit assertions. In this two-phase analysis, quantitative data were collected in the first phase through a large-scale survey to reveal general ideas and perceptions about the research problem. Qualitative data were collected through focus group interviews conducted with a smaller subset of participants to explore the research problem in depth during the second phase of this study.

Data Collection Instruments and Procedure

This study was conducted at a state university in Türkiye during the 2024-2025 academic year. The participants were EFL learners enrolled in the preparatory English program. Their proficiency levels varied from elementary (A1) to intermediate (B1), as defined by the CEFR. A total of 219 learners participated in the first phase of the study. 102 (46.6%) of the learners were female, and 117 (53.4%) of them were male. The ratio of women to men is relatively close. For the qualitative strand, 50 learners were chosen according to a convenience sampling method proposed by Etikan (2016), due to its accessibility to the participants and its appropriateness for this research study. Ethical approval was obtained, and all participants provided informed consent.

A structured survey, which included 5 Likert-scale to capture learners' motivational beliefs, attitudes, effort regulation and perceived challenges in language learning, was performed. The survey was piloted to enhance clarity and internal consistency. It was sent to 219 learners, and responses were collected anonymously via mail to promote integrity and reduce response bias. For the qualitative process, a semi-structured focus group interview using thematic prompts aligned with theoretical literature on L2 motivation was conducted.

Data Analysis

In the data analysis process, survey data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Frequencies and percentages were used to reveal learners' motivational patterns and preliminary themes. The qualitative data obtained from the focus group interviews, which were held with a small group, were analysed thematically, based on Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework to increase interaction and reflection. The integration of findings allowed a meta-level conclusion that enabled a more comprehensible and reliable understanding of the motivational trajectories of EFL learners.

Results

In this section, the qualitative and quantitative findings were presented under two subtitles. The first part presents data from the survey questions, and the second part presents the analysis of the focus group interviews.

Table 1

Data Analysis of Survey Questions

Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
	N %	N %	N %	N %	N %
1. I would like to speak English fluently.	2 0.9%	0 0%	2 0.9%	19 8.7%	196 89.5%
2. I would like to have English-speaking friends.	5 2.3%	3 1.4%	15 6.8%	55 25.1%	141 64.4%
3. I would like to communicate with someone who uses English.	3 1.4%	3 1.4%	17 7.8%	59 26.9%	137 62.6%
4. I would like to travel to English-speaking countries.	3 1.4%	1 0.5%	9 4.1%	16 7.3%	190 86.8%
5. I enjoy attending English classes.	11 5%	12 5.5%	70 32%	66 30.1%	60 27.4%
6. The subjects I learn in English classes are fun.	17 7.8%	17 7.8%	85 38.8%	58 26.5%	42 19.2%
7. I don't want to miss English classes.	20 9.1%	15 6.8%	68 31.1%	62 28.3%	54 24.7%
8. If I had the opportunity, I would take English lessons outside of school.	38 17.4%	30 13.7%	54 24.7%	38 17.14%	59 26.9%
9. English course topics are interesting.	18 8.2%	27 12.3%	75 34.2%	55 25.1%	44 20.1%
10. English lessons are necessary for me to find a job.	2 0.9%	1 0.5%	6 2.7%	18 8.2%	192 87.7%
11. Learning English will help me advance in my career.	2 0.9%	0 0%	7 3.2%	11 5%	199 90.9%
12. I believe that learning English will help me find a job abroad.	2 0.9%	0 0%	8 3.7%	21 9.6%	188 85.8%
13. I believe that I am skilled at communicating in English.	18 8.2%	18 8.2%	68 31.1%	49 22.4%	66 30.1%
14. I believe that I will be competent in communicating effectively in English.	7 3.2%	11 5%	50 22.8%	72 32.9%	79 36.6%
15. I believe that I am capable of understanding what is taught in class.	7 3.2%	11 5%	43 19.6%	77 35.2%	81 37%

These results reveal that the majority of the learners (around 90% total for agree and strongly agree combined) have the motivation to learn and communicate in English. They are eager to interact with English-speaking people. However, their motivation level decreases in the

classroom setting, as evidenced by the reduced agree and strongly agree responses regarding classes (less than 60% combined). The responses to questions, related to the English classroom atmosphere, the subjects and the methods, are scattered among neutral to strongly agree, which means that although they are highly motivated in learning English, they are less motivated to attend English classes.

The majority of the learners believe in the necessity of learning English in their career paths (90.9%) and in finding a good job (85.8%). On the other hand, the percentages of their responses to the questions related to their perceived competency in communicating in English and understanding English courses are again scattered among the options.

A remarkable inference from the responses of the learners is that even though they do not find English courses fun and are not so eager to attend the lessons, their responses to question 8 (If I had the opportunity, I would take English lessons outside of school) may show that their lack of motivation is not due to classes at school, but to the English teaching methods and content in general. Their responses to question 8, from strongly disagree to agree strongly, are 17.4%, 13.7%, 24.7%, 17.14% and 26.9%, respectively. This demonstrates that the way the English lesson is conducted, independent of the classroom atmosphere, decreases their motivation.

Data Analysis of Focus Group Interviews

In this study, focus group interviews were chosen as the qualitative method in order to evaluate the learners' motivations in learning English. Thematic analysis of the learners' responses provided a deeper understanding of the underlying dynamics that shape their motivation. The learners' responses were first coded and then categorised into themes and subthemes, which will be presented in this section.

Table 2

Data Analysis of Interview Question 1

Q1. Please explain your motivation for learning English.

Themes	Sub-themes
High motivation 27%	Career aspirations International opportunities Desire for personal development
Moderate motivation 44%	Demanding course schedule Time management challenge Fluctuating interest
Low motivation 27%	Monotony-boredom in classrooms Lack of internal and external motivational support

The data derived from the responses to the first question were categorised into three overarching categories: high motivation, moderate motivation and low motivation. Subsequently, several subthemes within each category emerged during the analysis, providing a clear and detailed explanation of the factors that shape learners' motivation.

Learners demonstrating high motivation tended to have forward-looking goals such as career goals, international opportunities and a desire for personal development. These motivational drivers emphasise the strong connection between long-term goals related to professional development and high motivation.

On the other hand, learners with moderate motivation showed a fluctuating motivation that is more dynamic and context-dependent. Their responses showed that they have the motivation to learn English, yet this motivation may be influenced by institutional and academic factors.

Responses associated with low motivation indicate the demotivating factors, which are monotony and boredom in classroom routines and a lack of internal and external motivational support. These responses show the influence of classroom dynamics and insufficient encouragement on learners' motivational levels. Some learners' verbatim driven from the data as an example of low motivation are: "There is nothing that motivates me", "I am reluctant to attend lessons. There are no external factors that challenge me", "I would like to learn, but there isn't a clear goal that guides me".

Table 3

Data Analysis of Interview Question 2

Q2. What are the factors that motivate you in learning English?

Themes	%
Career opportunities	35
International job opportunities	20
Personal Development	15
Instructor and classroom support	10

The second interview question examines the factors that motivate learners in learning English and from the data, four essential themes emerged. As shown in the table, career opportunities were the top motivator with 35%. As one of the learners mentioned, "English will help to increase my opportunity to find a job". In addition, international job opportunities follow it with 20%, which reflects the desire for global career advancements. For instance, one of the learners mentioned this as "Working abroad is very critical for my career." Personal development was another motivator mentioned by 15% of the learners. An example excerpt from the learners is: "Learning a new language improves my confidence." Finally, 10% of the learners highlighted the role of the instructor and classroom support as important factors in creating a positive learning environment.

Table 4

Data Analysis of Interview Question 3

Q3. Please explain the factors that decrease your motivation.

Themes	%
Excessive class hours	30
Exam difficulty and low marks	20
Complexity of language and vocabulary learning	16
Instructor attitude	10
Social pressure and absenteeism	8

The most demotivating factor mentioned by the learners was excessive class hours, with 30%. This reveals that learners are overwhelmed with long and intense classroom schedules, which negatively affect their motivation. Example excerpts from the learners are "Long hours of lessons are tiring" or "Long hours of classroom schedule lower my motivation". Another crucial factor that undermines motivation is exam difficulty and low marks, with 20%. This anxiety diminishes their self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation. As one of the learners said, "My motivation decreases, especially when my scores are low in exams".

The challenge of learning a new language, especially vocabulary learning, emerged as another theme mentioned by 16% of the learners. Some learners struggle with the memorisation of new vocabulary, which directly affects their fluency in language and hinders their motivation in the learning process. As one of the learners mentioned, "The number of words that I don't know is too high, and this demotivates me".

10% learners expressed the instructor's attitude as another factor that diminishes motivation. The role of instructors in establishing an inclusive and supportive learning environment and in providing positive reinforcement is crucial in the engagement of the learners. Finally, social pressure and absenteeism are other factors mentioned by 8% of the learners that stress the importance of a sense of belonging in the learning process.

Table 5

Data Analysis of Interview Question 4

Q4. What do you think will increase your motivation level?

Themes	%
Reduction of class hours	20
Entertaining- fun activities	18
Speaking practice	16
Instructor attitude	12
Collaboration and peer interaction	10

The results of question four indicate that structural and pedagogical factors impact learners' motivation. The reduction of class hours (20%) was the most prominent theme that emerged from the data, showing that excessive class hours are perceived as demanding and cause motivational decline. For instance, one of the learners attributed, "I feel more motivated if my classroom hours are fewer." Furthermore, entertaining and fun classroom activities were highlighted by 18% of the learners, which stresses the importance of interactive pedagogical approaches in creating a more stimulating and highly participatory atmosphere. As one of the learners said, "Games like Kahoot increase my motivation". 16% of the learners emphasised their need for speaking practice to actively use the language. An example from the learners' excerpt is "If we make more speaking practice, I would express myself better". This shows that learners need a more communicative and interactive learning atmosphere. Instructor attitude 12% and collaboration and peer interaction 10% were also reported as motivational contributors that clearly put forth the significance of instructional practices and positive, supportive classroom atmosphere.

Table 6

Data Analysis of Interview Question 5

Q5. Please explain the factors that negatively affect your motivation in the classroom.

Themes	%
An excessive number of class hours	15
Instructors' fast pace of lessons	11
Lack of participation in the classroom	10
Anxiety of exams and falling behind in the classroom	9

According to the learners, several key factors negatively influence motivation in the classroom. Notably, an excessive number of class hours emerged as learners felt overwhelmed. As one of the learners mentioned, "The sheer number of class hours makes it difficult for me to follow my daily plan and decreases my motivation." In addition, instructors' fast pace of lessons creates the feeling of falling behind. An example from an excerpt of one of the learners is "Intense and quick lesson process makes it harder for me to understand, and this lowers my motivation". Furthermore, lack of participation and anxiety about exams and falling behind diminishes motivation as they feel disconnected and experience anxiety and lack of confidence. Some of the learners' excerpts are "When my friends do not participate in the classroom, I feel like I'm falling behind", "Getting low marks in the exams undermines my self-confidence, and that affects my motivation negatively".

Discussion

The aim of this study is to examine the dynamics of motivation towards learning English among students enrolled in a university English preparatory programme, as well as the factors that increase or decrease motivation. The research findings indicate that students generally possess strong motivation to learn English, but this motivation can be influenced by various individual and contextual factors. These results largely correspond with previous research emphasising the central role of motivation in foreign language learning (Dörnyei, 2020; Gardner, 2010).

When quantitative data is examined, it is evident that the vast majority of students wish to speak English fluently, desire to communicate with English speakers and aim to travel to English-speaking countries. This finding indicates that students possess a significant degree of integrated motivation. According to Gardner's socio-educational model, integrated motivation is related to students' interest in the culture and society where the target language is spoken (Gardner, 1985; Gardner, 2010). The findings obtained in this study reveal that students view English not only as an academic requirement but also as an important tool for international communication and cultural interaction. This result is also consistent with studies showing that EFL learners perceive English as a global language of communication (Kormos & Csizér, 2008).

However, the findings reveal that students' motivation is also influenced significantly by instrumental factors. The vast majority of students believe that English will increase their job opportunities and contribute to their career development. This indicates that instrumental motivation plays an important role in students' motivation to learn English. According to Gardner's model, instrumental motivation is related to individuals learning a language for pragmatic purposes such as career opportunities or academic success (Gardner, 2010). The findings of this study also show that students directly associate English with future professional opportunities. Similarly, Kormos and Csizér (2008) state that students' future career goals significantly influence their motivation to learn a language.

The qualitative findings of the study also revealed that students' motivation levels varied. While some participants reported having high motivation, a significant proportion stated that their motivation was at a moderate level. This finding is consistent with studies emphasising that motivation is a dynamic process that can change over time rather than a fixed characteristic (Dörnyei, 2009; Dörnyei and Ryan, 2015). It appears that students' motivation can vary depending on their learning experiences, the classroom environment and their personal goals.

The qualitative findings also indicate that career opportunities, opportunities to work abroad and personal development goals are among the primary factors that increase students' motivation. These results are consistent with studies emphasising that language learning motivation is closely related to individuals' future goals and self-concept (Dörnyei, 2009; Ushioda, 2011). In particular, students' perception of English as being important for international communication and career opportunities emerged as a significant factor in increasing motivation. This can be explained by students' belief that English, as a global language of communication, will play an important role in their future social and professional lives.

On the other hand, research findings indicate that certain factors negatively affect students' motivation. In particular, excessive class hours, difficult examinations and the difficulty of learning vocabulary are among the significant factors that reduce student motivation. These findings are consistent with studies indicating that exam anxiety and learning difficulties can negatively affect motivation in the language learning process (MacIntyre, 2002; Öztürk and Gürbüz, 2013). In particular, it has been observed that receiving low grades on exams damages students' self-confidence and reduces their motivation. This situation can also be linked to

Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, which emphasises that students' perceptions of self-efficacy play an important role in motivation.

In addition, factors related to the classroom environment have been found to have a significant impact on motivation. Students have stated that factors such as the intensity of class hours, teachers covering topics too quickly and low levels of classroom participation negatively affect their motivation. This finding is consistent with studies emphasising the impact of teaching methods and the classroom environment on motivation (Lamb, 2017; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011). It is known that students have higher levels of motivation in more interactive and student-centred learning environments. Therefore, it can be said that communication-based activities and practices that increase student participation in the classroom can boost motivation.

Another important finding of the study is that students indicated they would like to engage in more speaking practices, participate in enjoyable learning activities and be in learning environments that involve social interaction in order to increase their motivation. This result is consistent with studies indicating that student-centred teaching approaches have positive effects on motivation (Lamb, 2017). In particular, gamification, group work and communication-based activities have been found to increase student motivation. In this context, teachers using methods that encourage active student participation in the classroom environment can play an important role in increasing motivation.

Overall, the findings of this study indicate that language learning motivation is a multidimensional construct influenced by individual, academic and social factors. Students' motivation is affected by both internal and external factors. This result is consistent with studies that reveal the internal and external dimensions of motivation working together within the framework of Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci, 2017; Noels, 2013). In this context, it is important to develop teaching strategies that both support students' intrinsic interests and strengthen their future-oriented goals in order to increase their motivation.

In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrate that the motivation of university preparatory school students to learn English is closely related to both individual goals and the learning environment. To increase student motivation, it may be advisable for teaching programmes to include more interactive, student-centred and communication-focused activities. Furthermore, increasing opportunities for students to use English in real-life contexts may also be important for sustaining motivation. These findings suggest that creating learning environments that support motivation in university preparatory programmes can positively influence students' language learning processes.

Conclusion

This study aimed to examine the dynamics of motivation towards learning English among students enrolled in a university English preparatory programme and the factors influencing this motivation. The research findings reveal that students generally have a high level of motivation to learn English. In particular, the desire to speak English fluently, the desire to communicate with English speakers, and the desire to visit English-speaking countries indicate that students have a strong motivation to learn the language. Furthermore, the majority of students believe that learning English will increase their career opportunities and contribute to their future professional development. This indicates that students' motivation includes both intrinsic and instrumental motivation elements.

However, the research findings also revealed that certain factors can negatively affect students' motivation. In particular, the intensity of class hours, the difficulty of exams, the difficulty of learning vocabulary and in some cases, the rapid pace of teaching processes are among the factors that reduce student motivation. Qualitative data also showed that classroom environments based on interactive and enjoyable learning activities, where

students can practise speaking more, can increase their motivation. These findings reveal that language learning motivation is significantly influenced not only by individual factors but also by contextual elements such as the learning environment and teaching methods.

Based on the findings of this research, certain pedagogical conclusions can be drawn. First, it can be recommended that teachers utilise student-centred and interaction-based teaching methods more frequently to increase student motivation. In particular, conversation-focused activities, group work, gamification applications and communication-based activities can increase student participation in lessons. Furthermore, increasing learning opportunities, where students can use English in real-life contexts, may be important for sustaining motivation. In this context, preparatory programmes that include learning activities related to students' academic and professional goals can support motivation.

This study also has certain limitations. The research was conducted only with students enrolled in the preparatory programme at a single university. This may limit the generalisability of the findings. Furthermore, quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, and more comprehensive statistical analyses were not performed. In addition, the qualitative data collection process was limited to focus group discussions with a smaller number of participants.

Future research conducted with larger samples from different universities could increase the generalisability of the findings. Also, longitudinal studies examining how students' motivation changes over time can contribute to a better understanding of the dynamic nature of motivation. In addition, research examining the effects of teaching methods, teacher motivation strategies and the classroom environment on student motivation can also make important contributions to the literature. Such studies can help develop more effective teaching practices that support student motivation in university preparatory programmes.

Disclosure of AI Usage

During the preparation of this work, the author used Grammarly for the purpose of language polishing for all sections. The final version remains the sole responsibility of the authors.

Ethical Declaration and Committee Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of scientific research and publication ethics. Ethical approval for this research was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the researchers' affiliated university.

Proportion of Authors' Contribution

Author 1: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Data Collection, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft.

Author 2: Conceptualisation, Review & Editing, Visualisation, Final Draft.

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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